

The unconcealed machine: on the aesthetics of the Klavierautomat

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyses the Klavierautomat (piano automaton), a robotic piano player, framing it as a complex cultural artefact with a productive aesthetic and philosophical ambiguity. The analysis synthesises insights from the philosophy of technology, media theory, and hauntology to theorise the tension between the instrument's material presence and its spectral effects. This theoretical framework is explored through two original, practice-based case studies. The first, *Etüden für Klavierautomat*, showcases the instrument's capacity for inhuman precision and speed, realising a technological sublime of computational perfection. In contrast, the second study, *Stuttering Calls of the Unencoded*, leverages systemic failure and feedback loops, exposing the Klavierautomat as a medium for a hauntological sublime found in the glitches and spectral residues of a flawed digital-mechanical translation process. The tension between these two artistic approaches reveals a wide aesthetic range of the instrument, from a tool for realising flawless logic to a medium for channelling hauntological imperfection. This capacity renders the Klavierautomat a liminal object, one that gives physical and acoustic form to algorithmic processes while staging the spectral haunting of its own mechanical nature.

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Introduction

The Klavierautomat (piano automaton) is a portable device that can be placed on the keyboard of any ordinary piano (see [Figure 1](#)). As a self-playing, computer-controlled robotic instrument, it extends the acoustic piano into the realm of algorithmic music, supporting an artistic approach that integrates technical and musical thinking with performance design. One key quality lies in its capacity to realise music that far exceeds human capabilities in speed, polyphonic density, and mechanical precision, enabling compositional approaches impossible for traditional performance. The instrument's theatrical presence is equally significant. By deliberately exposing its circuitry, wiring, and mechanical

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Figure 1. The Klavierautomat, mounted on a grand piano.

components, it invites dramaturgical strategies in staging, turning technical function into an artistic act by revealing its own materiality.

The Klavierautomat was conceived and developed by Austrian artist and researcher Winfried Ritsch. One of the devices that Ritsch built was acquired by the Institute of Computer Music and Sound Technology (ICST) in Zurich.¹ A practice-based research project at the ICST examines the properties of this instrument and their impact on musical expression and artistic working processes. The Klavierautomat has been showcased in several concert performances, sound installations, and on stage in a theatre production.

This article describes the Klavierautomat, its origins, and technical details, and situates it within a historical and cultural context. More broadly, it positions the instrument within the interdisciplinary research orientation of Creative Robotics Theatre, which addresses the aesthetic, dramaturgical, and philosophical dimensions of robotic systems that operate as performers or theatrical agents in their own right. The analysis arises from the authors' artistic and technical involvement with the Klavierautomat. To illustrate this engagement, two works that highlight their creative interaction with the Klavierautomat are presented as case studies. The Artist in Residence programme of the ICST, which is designed to foster collaboration and exchange with the artistic community, provided the framework for the creation and presentation of these works. Following an intensive two-week development period in the spring of 2025, a concert took place on 8 April 2025 at Kunstraum Walcheturm in Zurich. It featured works for the Klavierautomat by the two authors, alongside contributions by Lara Stanic, Micha Seidenberg, and Pascal Lund-Jensen.

The Klavierautomat

The creation of the Klavierautomat was motivated by the need to realise musical works conceived for a self-playing piano but whose technical demands exceeded the physical and mechanical limitations of devices such as the Yamaha Disklavier or the Bösendorfer SE that were commercially available at that time. Since these instruments were primarily designed to replicate the performance of human pianists, they permitted only a limited number of keys to be played simultaneously. The compositional visions of the Austrian composer Peter Ablinger provided the initial impetus for the development of the Klavierautomat. In his work cycle *Quadraturen*,² Ablinger performs spectral analyses of audio

recordings, subsequently reducing and quantising the frequency data into a format playable on an acoustic instrument.

This process may be interpreted as a form of sonic ‘pixelation,’ wherein the continuous frequencies of a recording are discretised into a dense array of pitches and articulations.

Especially if this procedure utilises speech as source material and attempts to effectively reproduce the sound of a voice, an enormous number of simultaneously played notes is necessary. This eventually led to the need to build a new instrument (Ritsch 2011).

Another guiding principle in the development of the Klavierautomat was the desire for flexibility and portability. Rather than integrating playback technology into a piano, Ritsch decided to construct a stand-alone device – a so-called ‘robot piano player’ – to be placed on top of any standard piano keyboard. This approach offered significant practical advantages. Designing a device that could interface with any existing instruments facilitated broader applicability and simplified transportation. After constructing two prototypes, Ritsch finalised the design and named the resulting device *Rhea*. He ultimately produced twelve units, one of which was acquired by the Institute of Computer Music and Sound Technology in Zurich in 2018.

In 2024, the Zurich Institute of Computer Music and Sound Technology, in collaboration with the Institute of Product Development and Production Technologies (IPP) of the Zurich University of Applied Sciences, developed an additional device to operate the piano’s sustain pedal.

This development followed the desire to utilise the tonal possibilities of the piano pedal as well.

This was a request frequently made by artists who were involved with the Klavierautomat.

The Klavierautomat consists of 88 solenoids to strike the keys of the piano keyboard. These solenoids are attached to a robust metal frame mounted on a piano with two clamps on both sides. The tips of the solenoids are cushioned with felt to prevent unwanted noise. The Klavierautomat is equipped with three microcontroller boards. This is necessary because each board can only control up to 16 solenoids. The output of each board is amplified by FET drivers to provide the voltage required by the solenoids. The first board functions as the master unit, receiving commands via an Ethernet

Figure 2. The solenoids (left), one of three microcontroller boards (middle), and one of the clamps to fix the automaton to a piano (right).

Figure 3. The device to operate a piano's sustain pedal.

connection. It then actuates the connected solenoids or forwards the commands to the two slave boards accordingly. The details of the piano automaton are depicted in [Figure 2](#). The device that operates the sustain pedal consists of a stepper motor that drives a snail-shaped cam positioned above the pedal. As the motor rotates the cam, it depresses the pedal. This rotary actuation method provides greater precision compared to a linear actuator. It supports differentiated control, enabling advanced techniques such as the gradual depression of the pedal at an arbitrary slow speed and 'half-pedal' effects (see [Figure 3](#)).

To perform music on the Klavierautomat, a dedicated control software is required. This software runs on a separate computer and interfaces with the Automaton by sending commands to the microcontroller boards over Ethernet. It can receive note-on, note-off, and pedal-position messages via the Open Sound Control (OSC) protocol, allowing any OSC-compatible application to drive the system or run generative algorithms. In addition, the control software can read and play MIDI files. A key function of the control software is data mapping. Each musical note must be linked to its corresponding solenoid, and the received velocity value must be scaled appropriately to produce the desired loudness. Since the Klavierautomat's position relative to the keyboard can vary slightly due to the different shapes of the pianos, and, even more importantly, the velocity-to-loudness response differs significantly across the solenoids, precise calibration is required before use. A flowchart of the entire control system is depicted in [Figure 4](#).

Machine music questioning human agency

The Klavierautomat, as a music-playing machine, is embedded in a long history of music automata. There exists an ancient and significant connection between music and technology. Thor Magnusson argues that music-making has always been at the forefront of human tool use, stating: '[I]f there is anything that might best exemplify human nature, it might be our technologies for musical expression' (Magnusson 2019, 1). The desire to

Figure 4. Flow chart of the control system of the Klavierautomat.

delegate music to non-human agents and capture the temporal sequence of music in a programme gave rise to music automata. These devices, which prefigure modern digital music playback, have a long history, predating other inventions such as the programmable loom and the mechanical calculator.

The earliest known design for a programmable machine is the automatic flute player described by the three Banū Mūsā brothers, who lived in 9th-century Baghdad.³ From the fourteenth century onwards, descriptions of programmable carillons attached to mechanical clocks can be found. Parallel to the development of carillons, programmed music was frequently integrated into astronomical clocks from the fifteenth century onwards.

Music automata, so-called music boxes, orchestrions, and flute clocks, are an underrated chapter in European music history. These musical machines, whose technical sophistication developed in parallel with advances in clockmaking, held a great fascination for people. Several composers of the eighteenth century, including George Frideric Handel, Joseph Haydn, Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart, and Ludwig van Beethoven, were fascinated by these automata and wrote original compositions for them.

Mechanical musical instruments became increasingly widespread, reaching their peak between the mid-nineteenth century and the First World War (Reidemeister 2010, 65). Around 1880, the revolving cylinder with pins was replaced as an information carrier by pneumatically scanned perforated strips, which were initially made of cardboard and later of paper. Player pianos are a special form of these musical automata. In their form as 'reproduction pianos', they were used to reproduce the recorded playing of famous pianists. In the twentieth century, some composers began to write music specifically for these automatic pianos. Around 1920, a strong interest in the mechanical reproduction of music emerged in many places. It focused on two aspects: first, the objectivity that could be achieved by avoiding human performers, and second, the new aesthetic

made possible by overcoming human limitations. 'For the immediate future there will be only two kinds of music, the banal and the mechanistic,' predicted Antheil (1922).

In 1926, at the famous German festival for contemporary music in Donaueschingen, one concert was dedicated explicitly to 'original compositions for mechanical instruments'. This concert featured works written specifically for the 'Welte-Mignon', a widely used player piano of that time. The following year, the festival relocated to Baden-Baden, and another concert entitled 'original works for mechanical instruments' took place. The composer Paul Hindemith, a leading figure in this festival, praised in a programme note the qualities of the self-playing piano: 'The advantages of the apparatus lie simply in its absolute unambiguousness, clarity, cleanliness, and high degree of precision – qualities that human play does not possess and does not need.'⁴ (Hindemith 1994, 22).

Earlier in the century, between 1916 and 1919, the American composer Henry Cowell, still studying with Charles Seeger, wrote his remarkable text *New Musical Resources*, which was published in revised form as a book in 1930. In the chapter about rhythm, Cowell speculates on how complex polyrhythms and polymetres could be based on the proportions found in the harmonic series, thereby relating musical time to musical pitch. He concludes that '[s]ome of the rhythms developed through the present acoustical investigation could not be played by any living performer; but these highly engrossing rhythmical complexes could easily be cut on a player-piano roll.' (Cowell 1996, 204). This statement had a significant impact, as it inspired Conlon Nancarrow to use the player piano for his compositions (Duckworth 1995, 40).

In fact, Nancarrow became one of the most important composers to explore the player piano and develop an idiosyncratic language for it. At some point in his career, frustrated by the unsatisfactory performances of his rhythmically demanding music, he decided to follow Cowell's advice and to compose only pieces for the self-playing piano henceforth. This allowed him to circumvent the limits of human accuracy and speed, following his long-standing wish: 'ever since I'd been writing music I was dreaming of getting rid of the performers.' (Nancarrow, quoted in Amirkhanian 1977, 15).

Nancarrow's *Studies for Player Piano*, characterised by artificial gestures such as absurdly fast runs and leaps, as well as the simultaneity of different tempos – including rhythmical proportions that use irrational numbers, such as pi or the square root of two – embody 'machine music' in its purest form. Furthermore, they are also a good example of the mutual influence of technology and compositional working methods. With the player piano, Nancarrow was able to overcome the limits of human accuracy and speed. However, it would be a hasty conclusion to assume that this automatically led to unrestricted freedom. Nancarrow had to craft the piano roll by hand in a meticulous and time-consuming process, punching each hole with millimetre precision. For this, Nancarrow first needed to determine the tempo structure of the piece and draw the time scales on a blank music roll, indicating the position on the time axis where the holes had to be punched. Transferring these time scales to the music roll could already take several months for complex compositions. Only then did the 'actual composing' begin, during which he organised the pitches (Kocher 2023, 190–192). The entire workflow was a lengthy process that required careful planning in advance and, particularly concerning the time structure, left no room for spontaneity or changes at a later stage. The liberation from the constraints of human performance imposed other constraints.

The player piano achieves a high level of precision at the cost of a more immediate, tactile sense of human control. This may be regarded as a lack of capacity to convey the expressive dimension of music. Nancarrow, however, explored these characteristics and turned them into an aesthetic advantage. Rather than trying to compensate for the instrument's limitations, he emphasised them by modifying the timbre of his two upright player pianos by adding tacks to the hammers on one and strips of leather to the other. The resulting sound was sharper, more metallic, and more aggressive. These changes enhanced rhythmic clarity and attack, but above all, they emphasised the mechanical nature of the instrument and, therefore, distanced it from its traditional milieu (Reynolds 1984, 19–20).

Another aspect that mirrors the transgression of human capabilities, which manifests itself in the exaggerated virtuosity, high speed, and loud volume the player piano can produce, is the overload of the listener's perceptual abilities. Therefore, Nancarrow's pieces reveal a dehumanisation in their compositional techniques, which take into account neither the limitations of the performer nor those of the listener, resulting in a transcendence of the constitution of human beings. Some scholars have interpreted this process of transcending human limits by using a term traditionally used to describe the excessive and incomprehensible in art: the sublime. However, the sublime qualities of Nancarrow's work have less to do with nature, which traditionally embodies the sublime, than with technology, which has replaced nature in the modern imagination (Drott 2004; Herzfeld 2007).

The history of music automata illustrates how technology has long shaped musical thought and practice. From early mechanical instruments to the precision of the player piano, composers have utilised machines to expand musical expression beyond human capabilities. The player piano, in particular, proved to be not only a sophisticated technical device but also a platform for aesthetic experimentation, most notably expressed in Nancarrow's works, which question human agency in art and redefine what it means to compose, perform, and perceive music.

An ambiguous cultural artefact

Building upon the technical and historical accounts we presented earlier, this section now focuses on the Klavierautomat's role as a complex cultural artefact, examining the nexus of the piano, the robotic mechanism, the programmer/composer, and the audience as a unique assemblage that sustains multifarious cultural relations. Within the emerging field of Creative Robotics Theatre, Gemeinboeck and Saunders (2025) have theorised such assemblages as sites of 'more-than-human' entanglement, using performance-making to inquire into the embodied relationships that arise when human and robotic bodies share a stage. The Klavierautomat, however, stages a fundamentally different kind of entanglement, one defined by displacement, where the robotic mechanism supplants the human performer and absence itself becomes the structuring condition of the emerging cultural relations. This condition demands a theoretical apparatus attuned to spectrality and trace. We therefore draw from Simondon's philosophy of technology, Heidegger's phenomenology, cybernetic art, Derrida's concept of hauntology, and Kittler's and Kwastek's theorisations of the interface to unpack the Klavierautomat's role as a medium haunted by the spectre of the absent performer.

While the traditional piano reconfigured music around the expressive capabilities of the human performer, the piano player, and subsequently the Klavierautomat, extends this instrumental lineage into the purely computational realm. Applying Marshall McLuhan's tetrad of media effects, the Klavierautomat enhances the musical parameters of speed, density, precision, and polyphonic complexity to a superhuman degree, fully realising the algorithmic potential that emerged with the player piano's transition from mechanical to digital technology. It obsolesces the traditional role of the human performer as an interpretive and physiological mediator between the compositional idea and its sonic realisation. It retrieves an ideal first made tangible by the player piano, treating music as a pure mechanism in which sound is a direct manifestation of a mathematical or logical process, akin to the intricate music automata of the past. Finally, when pushed to its extreme, the Klavierautomat has the potential to reverse from a medium for musical composition into an advanced data sonification engine, where the 'music' becomes a secondary effect to the primary message of demonstrating algorithmic power or representing complex datasets. However, given that the Klavierautomat and its kin represent a highly specialised niche, this tetrad serves less as a description of an established cultural phenomenon and more as a speculative framework for understanding the instrument's potential transformative capacity.

McLuhan's tetrad helps us understand and anticipate the Klavierautomat's broader cultural effects. Simondon's philosophy of technology, however, provides a more fundamental ontological distinction by differentiating between tools and instruments based on the specific human faculties they enhance: '[B]y tool one understands the technical object enabling one to prolong and arm the body in order to accomplish a gesture, and by instrument the technical object that enables one to prolong and adapt the body in order to achieve better perception' (Simondon 2017, 130). In this sense, a piano augmented by the mechanised and computerised extensions of the Klavierautomat can be understood as both a tool and an instrument, simultaneously amplifying compositional gestures and enhancing the sensory apprehension of complex, algorithmically generated polyphonic textures.

While Simondon's distinction focuses on the human faculties of perception and action, Heidegger's polarity between equipment (*Zeug*) and the work of art (*Werk*) offers a different path, focusing instead on the object's own mode of being. The Klavierautomat's enigmatic nature is corroborated by its position at the intersection of both these conceptual pairs. For Heidegger, the essence of equipment is to withdraw in its serviceability. The artwork, however, has the unique power to bring this withdrawn nature into unconcealment. The artwork, in this view, stages a profound event of revelation, showing us the true nature of the equipment and the world it inhabits. As Heidegger puts it: 'We allow a work to tell us what equipment is. By this means, it came to light what is at work in the work: the opening up of beings in their being, the happening of truth' (Heidegger 2002, 18). 'Truth' in this context should be understood through the Greek concept of 'aletheia', which etymologically means unconcealment or disclosure. For Heidegger, this truth is a dynamic 'happening,' an event in which a being emerges from concealment and shows itself in its essence, in contrast to a static, factual correctness of a statement.

The Klavierautomat functions as reliable equipment when its machinery withdraws into the background, becoming a transparent and serviceable tool for the flawless execution of musical data. It brings this withdrawn nature into unconcealment,

however, when its non-human qualities, such as the audible clicks of its solenoids, the uncanny perfection of its algorithmic timing, or the massive density of notes it can play simultaneously, are brought into the foreground. In this moment, the apparatus itself begins to 'speak,' revealing the truth of its own emergent algorithmic and robotic world of pure computation, generative processes, and non-human temporalities. Through such inhuman manifestations, it reveals this world directly but also hints at its possibilities, anticipates its aesthetics, and prophesies a future where creativity is decoupled from biological embodiment.

The Klavierautomat's evocative visual and kinetic presence is central to its identity, creating a rich conceptual tension between the foundational cybernetic notion of the 'black box' and the exposed mechanics of process-based art. Systems theory defines a 'black box' as any system whose internal workings are opaque, revealing only its inputs and outputs while hiding the process that connects them. With its intricate mechanics of hammers, strings, and dampers hidden inside a polished case, and with the performer's minimal finger movements offering little hint of the complex causality within, the traditional piano exemplifies the quintessential black box. The Klavierautomat's design, however, performs a deliberate 'opening of the black box.' This gesture is a direct counterpoint to the logic of modern interfaces, which, as media theorist Friedrich Kittler notes, are designed to efface the material reality of the machine behind a user-friendly surface (Kittler 1999). This act of revealing the process aligns the Klavierautomat with the system's aesthetic of kinetic art, where artists like Jean Tinguely made the machine's operation itself the artistic statement (Pontus Hultén 1968). By exposing its workings, it presents the 'software' of the algorithmic concept and the 'hardware' of the physical mechanism as an inseparable whole (Burnham 1968), turning what Kittler calls the 'real' of the machine into a behavioural process that, as Roy Ascott argued, becomes a 'catalyst' for a new aesthetic experience (Ascott 1968).

Simondon argues that before a machine can exist as a concrete technical individual, humans perform its functional role. In this earlier phase, a human does not simply use a tool but is the technical being, the locus of organisation. Describing the historical shift, he states that 'man who in fact provisionally replaced the machine before truly technical individuals could emerge' comes to feel that the machine is usurping his role (Simondon 2017, 82). When the automated machine finally crystallises, and the human is no longer required for that function, a spectral residue of this prior human labour remains. In Derrida's terms, this residue acts as a spectre, haunting the present as a trace of the physically absent and thereby disrupting linear time while troubling the distinction between presence and absence (Derrida 1994). Algorithmicity is, in this sense, an inherently hauntological process, as it encodes and automates gestures that were once performed by living bodies. Sadie Plant powerfully argues that the history of computation is haunted by the spectre of the feminised labour of the weavers, typists, and 'human computers' whose meticulous, repetitive actions formed the operational precursors to digital technology (Plant 1997). The spectre is the forgotten, disavowed labour of the body that continues to secretly structure the operations of the machine.

This concept of technological spectrality directly applies to the Klavierautomat, where every performance is haunted by the ghost of the human pianist. The most immediate spectre is the visual uncanniness of the solenoids, which depress and release with human-like intention but without a human body. These solenoids, which Ritsch himself

tellingly describes as ‘electromechanical fingers’ complete with felt ‘finger tips’ (Ritsch 2011), each directly replace the action of a human finger, thereby exemplifying Derrida’s spectral trace. They mechanise and make visible the forgotten, disavowed labour of the pianist’s touch, encoding corporeal memory into mechanical repetition. Furthermore, the ghost of the virtuoso haunts the machine’s performance as an implicit, spectral benchmark. The Klavierautomat’s inhuman speed and precision are always measured against the remembered (but now absent) bodies of performers, whose corporeal constraints defined the fundamental meaning of virtuosity. The very musical language itself that the machine executes, e.g. crescendos, sforzandos, legato phrasing, is a vocabulary of physical gestures, spectral traces of tactility and interpretive feeling that are no longer present. Therefore, the Klavierautomat performs an uncanny drama, channeling the spectral repertoire of human expression and virtuosity through a non-human body, making the performer’s absence a palpable presence in the room.

German composer and director Heiner Goebbels offers an effective creative approach to this topic by formulating an ‘aesthetics of absence’ as a central principle of his theatrical work. He conceptualises this as an opportunity for a different kind of encounter, defined as ‘the presence of the other, as a confrontation with an unseen image or an unheard word or sound, an encounter with forces beyond man’s control, that are out of our reach’ (Goebbels 2015, 6). This principle reaches its most radical expression in his piece *Stifters Dinge* (Stifter’s Things), first performed in Lausanne, Switzerland, in 2007 and described as a composition for five pianos without pianists and a performance without performers. Here, Goebbels extends his compositional strategies into a fully theatrical dimension, confronting the audience with a stage where agency is transferred from human performers to the machinery itself (Eisner 2025). Light, sound, and autonomous stage mechanisms become the dramaturgical agents with their interactions forming the core of the performance. This focus is intensified by a stark operational division where all human voices emerge as spectral traces from the archive via loudspeakers, while all other sounds are produced in real time by the mechanical processes unfolding live on stage (Goebbels 2015, 29).

The spectral quality, staged so theatrically in Goebbels’s work, defines the core phenomenological dynamic of the Klavierautomat in action. It creates a fundamental instability in the viewers’ perception, preventing them from settling into a single, comfortable mode of reception. This refusal of passive reception is precisely what constitutes the Klavierautomat as an interactive system, even when it does not solicit conventional input. For the audience, the encounter is primarily perceptual, as the uncanny performance forces them into an active, interpretive dialogue with the machine. For the composer or live coder,⁵ the interaction is a direct, real-time feedback loop between generative algorithms and the instrument’s mechanical-acoustic response. The Klavierautomat has been deployed in various formats that emphasise different aspects of this dual framework, from sound installations where the machine performs autonomously (foregrounding perceptual interaction) to explicitly participatory works such as *Klavierspiel* (Kocher, Bisig, and Inauen 2019) and, more recently, *8811 spiel was Schönes* by Lara Stanic, which was part of the ‘Machine Musicianship’ concert and allowed audience members to trigger notes in real time via a mobile app.

Media art theorist Katja Kwastek defines this dynamic as the central aesthetic of interactive works, arguing that the experience ‘manifests itself in a process of oscillation

between flow and reflection, between absorption in the interaction and distanced (self-)perception, and between cathartic transformation and cognitive judgment' (Kwastek 2013, 162). This perpetual oscillation between engagement and analysis is the primary mechanism through which the Klavierautomat operates on its audience. The aesthetic experience of the Klavierautomat can therefore be understood through what Kwastek terms a 'phenomenology of interaction,' specifically through the concept of frame collision (Kwastek 2013). Frame collision, the simultaneous activation of multiple, conflicting interpretive frameworks, is a core theatrical mechanism that creates perceptual instability and self-reflexivity in performance (Carlson 2001; Fischer-Lichte 2008). The Klavierautomat's performance operates on two conflicting frames simultaneously, evoking the familiar frame of the 'piano recital' while also functioning as a 'technical demonstration' of mechanical precision and algorithmic logic. This collision disrupts any passive reception of the music, forcing the audience into a state of self-reflection about the nature of performance, labour, and creativity. Thus, the Klavierautomat operates in a mode of profound self-referential ambiguity, where the artistic act becomes the machine's performance of its own operational limits and possibilities.

In essence, the theories of Simondon, Heidegger, Derrida, and Kwastek allow us to analyse the Klavierautomat's significance as a cultural object that complicates the boundaries between tool and artwork, presence and absence, and human and machine. This framework illuminates the instrument's unique mode of existence, characterised by the unconcealment of its mechanics, the haunting of its performance, and the interactive frame collision it imposes on the listener/viewer. The following case studies will now put these theoretical insights into action, exploring how the authors have engaged with these inherent qualities to produce specific and novel aesthetic outcomes.

Case study 1

To illustrate the technical possibilities of the Klavierautomat, explore a machine-based performance practice, and find possibilities for machine-based musical expression, one of the authors realised six short pieces entitled *Etüden für Klavierautomat* ('études for piano automaton').⁶ Each etude lasts between 1.5 and 2 min, focuses on a single idea – be it a technical aspect, an acoustic phenomenon, or a generative musical concept – and is formally structured through a procedural, often goal-oriented development. All etudes are generated in real time by a computer programme, adding another conceptual layer to the idea of machine music.

Etüde #1 ('moiré')

This etude is about temporal precision. 14 Keys (the pitches E and F in all octaves across the piano's full range) are played repeatedly. The speed at which these keys are played is steady, but distinct for each key. The inter-onset intervals of these repetitions are 198, 199, 200 ms, and so on up to 211 ms. Even though the tempo of each note is consistent, the slight differences among them give rise to slowly changing moiré-like interference patterns. Harmonically, the music is reduced to only two pitch classes (E and F). This tonal reduction serves to focus the listener's attention on the temporal phenomena. By

superimposing several nearly identical tempos, this etude relates to the concept of 'phasing' in minimal music.

Etüde #2 ('scales')

This etude explores the effect of harmonic colouration that emerges when monophonic music is played at high speed. It consists of descending gestures that span the entire keyboard.

The speed at which these gestures are executed slowly oscillates between 20 and 200 notes per second. The pitch material is organised by dividing the 88 keys of the piano into four groups of 22 keys. A pattern of ten intervals is randomly generated and applied to each of these groups to produce a set of notes. These notes are then played in a rapid downward movement.

Once the lowest note is reached, a new interval pattern is generated, initiating the next descending gesture. Each new pattern introduces a subtle variation in the harmonic colour, thereby shaping a continuously evolving sonic texture. Over the course of the piece, there is a gradual reduction in the size of these interval patterns. As a result, the descending gestures become increasingly sparse and fragmented. The etude ends when the pattern size reaches zero.

Etüde #3 ('shadows')

The core idea of this etude is auditory masking, i.e. the effect of a louder sound obscuring a quieter one that occurs simultaneously or nearby in time. Throughout the piece, two chords are always played together: one is short and loud, the other calm and sustained. Through this pairing, a striking auditory effect is created: the loud chord masks the attack of the quiet one. The timbre of the piano is characterised by its attack and its percussive nature. The masking effect causes the quieter chord seemingly to lose its attack and take on an unreal, shadowy quality, as if these notes would emerge from nowhere. The chords themselves are randomly generated. The masked chord (the quiet, sustained one) alternates between tonal (often a minor triad) and atonal configurations, whereas the masking chord (the loud, short one) is always atonal.

Etüde #4 ('glissandi')

This etude explores the extreme speed and mechanical precision of the Klavierautomat. Chromatic scales are executed at a rate of 200 notes per second, creating a texture that sounds like a glissando. The keys are hit so quickly that some of them barely speak, which lends the music a fleeting and hasty character. The chromatic scales move up and down within a defined pitch range. Upon reaching the upper or lower boundary of this range, the direction of motion is reversed, producing a perpetual ascent and descent. A slower generative process redefines these pitch boundaries approximately every 0.5 s, selecting new values at random. This constant change of the pitch boundaries causes a continuous metamorphosis of the resulting gestures.

Etüde #5 ('stairs')

The fifth etude is inspired by Shepard tones, an auditory illusion named after cognitive scientist Roger Shepard. This illusion creates the perception of a tone that endlessly ascends or descends in pitch. When a Shepard tone ascends by one octave, the listener unmistakably perceives an upward motion, yet it paradoxically seems to arrive at the same pitch where it started. Typically, Shepard tones are generated electro-acoustically. In this etude, however, the illusion is approximated as closely as possible on an acoustic piano. Each pitch is doubled across all octaves of the instrument's range, with the middle octave sounding at maximum loudness and the volume tapering off toward the extremes. The etude begins with a straightforward ascending chromatic scale. As the piece progresses, this orderly motion becomes increasingly distorted. Initially, all melodic intervals are ascending minor seconds. Gradually, the probability of larger intervals increases. The occurrence of major seconds, minor thirds, major thirds, and even larger intervals becomes more frequent. This rising probability of broader intervals results in the emergence of diverse melodic patterns.

Etüde #6 ('repetitions')

This etude is about sound masses. A generative algorithm randomly chooses pitches, each of which is repeated 120 times at a randomly determined, yet steady rate. During a repetition process, the keystroke velocity gradually increases from minimum to maximum force. Because the repetition rates differ, the durations of each repetition process vary accordingly. Multiple such processes unfold simultaneously. As the piece progresses, the time between the initiation of new processes becomes shorter, resulting in a gradual thickening of the texture. The ever-increasing number of simultaneous pitches generates different sound colours and creates an effect vaguely resembling additive synthesis. This etude is not only a study in pitch accumulation but also an exploration of temporal complexity as the layering of different repetition rates yields a variety of intricate rhythmic textures.

The musical expression of these six etudes is based on the fact that they are liberated from the limitations of human execution. It is an expression unattainable by human performers and characterised by features such as speed, massiveness, and precision. In this sense, these etudes follow in Nancarrow's footsteps. By using generative algorithms, which are partly rule-based and partly random, to automate even the composition process, they advance one step further towards machine agency. This advancement is logical, as the characteristic of a non-human performance, particularly speed and massiveness, which are always associated with a large number of notes, can be effectively controlled with generative algorithms.

Case study 2

Whereas the first case study focused on revealing the Klavierautomat's mechanical, non-human affordances, this second case study explores its unpredictable and spectral dimensions through an analysis of *Stuttering Calls of the Unencoded*.⁷ This live-coding performance, realised by the other author, emerges from the complex interplay of feedback-

driven, digital-mechanical coupled systems. Here, the hauntological framework becomes the primary analytical lens, illuminating the spectral dimensions that haunt the Klavierautomat's algorithmic processes.

The performance environment itself is designed to immerse the audience directly within the feedback loop of the system, making viscerally perceptible the human-machine coupling. Arranged in a circle, eight loudspeakers position the piano with the Klavierautomat, the live coder, and the audience within the same acoustic space. Conceptually, the work draws inspiration from Peter Ablinger's *Quadraturen* (discussed earlier), employing the Klavierautomat as a mechanically activated acoustic resynthesizer. While digital audio synthesis typically attempts to model acoustic phenomena, this project's core provocation is to enact a fundamental reversal, using the acoustic piano to simulate purely computer-generated sounds.

Rather than striving for a successful translation, the work foregrounds the aesthetic potential of inevitable failure, making the discrepancies, miscalculations, glitches, and inconsistencies that emerge from this flawed process the primary aesthetic locus. Benford et al. (2025) have observed that artists working with robotic systems often embrace technological limitations as generative material instead of treating them as obstacles to overcome. *Stuttering Calls of the Unencoded* radicalises this principle. It does not repurpose constraints encountered during the creative process but deliberately manufactures systemic failure by design, strategically overloading the analysis algorithms with signals they were never intended to process and making the system's misbehaviour itself the work's primary compositional engine.

The technical setup is centred on the live coder, who synthesises and spatialises sonic flows to the eight-speaker array in real time. The synthetic sounds are primarily based on digital feedback loops, where the system's output is recursively fed back into its own input. This feedback signal is then used to modulate the sound synthesis, either through direct mathematical operations or by extracting perceptually significant characteristics via advanced algorithms and mapping them to synthesis parameters. Simultaneously, a custom suite of algorithms performs a continuous, multi-faceted analysis of the live coding environment's digital audio output. This suite employs a monophonic pitch tracker for glissandi and melodic contours, a polyphonic algorithm for identifying the four most prominent notes, and an FFT analysis to capture the spectral peaks of noisy textures. This analysed data is then converted to MIDI notes, generating a continuous stream that is transmitted in real time to the Klavierautomat via the OSC protocol. This digital-to-mechanical process, however, is only one part of the system's recursive architecture. Contact microphones placed inside the piano capture the acoustic sound of the Klavierautomat's performance. The live piano sound is fed back into the live coding environment, where its features are also extracted and injected into the sound synthesis parameters, creating a self-perpetuating interchange where the digital activates the acoustic and the acoustic, in turn, infects the digital. [Figure 5](#) shows the entire signal flow.

Throughout the performance, the live coder writes and modifies the sound synthesis code while simultaneously manipulating key parameters of both the synthesis and the analysis/resynthesis algorithms using a MIDI controller, acting as a cybernetic navigator that steers the entire unstable system through its own emergent turbulence. This transforms his role from a directive operator to an active co-conspirator, one deeply entangled in the system's own process of becoming. The coder is not simply imposing preconceived

Figure 5. Signal flow diagram of *Stuttering Calls of the Unencoded*, illustrating the dual feedback architecture (digital and acoustic) and the mediating visuals.

musical structures but is engaged in a transductive process where each coding decision propagates through the digital-acoustic network, catalysing phase shifts in the system's behaviour and iteratively shaping novel aesthetic realities (Giannoutakis 2025). The performance thus rejects top-down control, opting instead for a discursive relationship between human intention and machinic behaviour. In this dance of agencies (Pickering 1995), the coder's perceptual framework evolves as they listen for and respond to the system's inherent tendencies, discovering resolutions to emergent incompatibilities and guiding the entire digital-mechanical assemblage through its metastable states (Carey 2025). This approach allows musical manifestations to occur serendipitously, 'giving a reflexive distance to experience humans' innate technicalities on the one hand and the human reality that is immanent in the computational medium on the other' (Giannoutakis 2025).⁸

Applying the hauntological framework, *Stuttering Calls of the Unencoded* explores the spectral dimension that arises from what can only be described as a cursed translation. The work's central tension lies in a deliberate mismatch between its analytical algorithms, designed for clean signals, and the inherently messy nature of its sound sources of non-linear digital feedback and captured acoustic sound, which strategically overloads the system to elicit its glitches as aesthetic material. The residuals, remainders, and in-betweens that scientific rigour and engineering efficiency seek to exorcise are never truly absent. Here, the entire performance configuration is designed to provoke these phantoms to manifest and sing. This spectral process unfolds on multiple levels. First, there are the glitches and emergent noises born from the chaotic nature of the digital feedback itself. The analysis/resynthesis algorithm that generates the MIDI notes then gives birth to a second haunting, materialising a stuttering ghost in the data stream that appears as interruptions, misfired notes, and erratic bursts. Finally, the acoustic piano's attempt at mechanical reproduction is itself haunted by its own acoustic materiality. The sympathetic vibrations of strings, the percussive noise of the hammers, and the complex decay of tones collectively resist the clean, discrete commands of the MIDI data,

asserting their own physical, spectral reality. The performance thus becomes a conduit for these 'unencoded' signals, amplifying the stutters and glitches of the computational, transductive, and material ghosts as the work's primary voice.

Within this spectral economy, the live coder assumes an ambiguous and paradoxical role. While physically present, he functions as a surrogate for the very 'ghost of the human pianist' that the machine's performance invokes. A further layer of hauntological tension emerges as the audience witnesses the human coder's intentions being constantly distorted and subverted by the 'cursed translation' of the system he commands. The coder's own gestures, the meticulous typing and manipulation of faders and knobs, are themselves spectral, disembodied from the violent, physical act of the solenoids striking the keys. He is at once a ghost puppeteer and a navigator of the very phantoms he summons, a present performer whose primary struggle is with the spectral rebellions of his own extended, cognitive, and machinic body.

From the audience's perspective, the performance environment is designed for direct, visceral immersion, with the circular speaker array enveloping the listener in the system's chaotic behaviour. A scenographic element complements the sonic immersion through a large projection that displays live, close-up video feeds of both the Klavierautomat's solenoids and keys and the performer's hand gestures, with the computer code overlaid on this visual stream. This visual dramaturgy aligns with a foundational tenet of live coding practices, as established in the original 2004 TOPLAP manifesto, to 'Show us your screens' (Blackwell et al. 2022, 39). This practice rejects the mystique of the technological 'black box' by revealing the labour and logic of the performance, an act that resonates deeply with the very design of the Klavierautomat. The performance thus offers a nested transparency, exposing the conceptual labour, performative gestures, algorithmic mediation, and electromechanical materiality.

However, this transparency reveals a more unsettling dynamic. The audience witnesses a potent frame collision between the clean logic displayed on the screen and the glitch-ridden chaos erupting from the speakers and piano. The code appears rational and precise, yet the sonic output reveals constant failure. The analysis algorithms visibly struggle to interpret the messy feedback, generating a stuttering, erratic stream of commands. As the Klavierautomat attempts to execute these flawed instructions, its solenoids lurch between violent percussive seizures and ostentatious melodic runs. The aesthetic experience lies in this forced reconciliation, as the audience must oscillate between what they see and what they hear.

Sonically, the performance inhabits a volatile and textural landscape defined by the Klavierautomat's unstable mimicry of the digital synthesis. The generative audio, broadcast through the eight-speaker array, is derived from a single block of SuperCollider code. This code is an extensive modification of an SCTweet created by Batuhan Bozkurt (earslap).⁹ While Bozkurt's original code utilises a feedback signal to generate a pattern of ascending notes, the modified version mutates this sound synthesis algorithm into a continuous, tense drone that is prone to unpredictable eruptions of dense, noisy glitches with sharp, digital attacks. During the performance, the coder progressively corrupts the drone through live-coded interventions, using feedback-driven phase modulation to distort its ethereal quality while employing a digital feedback delay network to elicit emergent, ghost-like frequencies. The Klavierautomat's response is brutally literal yet musically complex. It initially mirrors the drone's fundamental frequency, repeatedly

striking the corresponding key, but as glitches erupt or new frequencies emerge, it violently switches registers, translating these digital events into aggressive melodic gestures. In the densest, noisiest sections, the FFT tracking algorithm is engaged, prompting the Klavierautomat to perform dense chromatic clusters, translating the digital noise into a thick, percussive blur of acoustic sound. Other improvisational moments revolve around coding looping glissandi gestures for the drone. The Klavierautomat creates a form of discretised reverberation by simultaneously following the sweeping gestures and introducing micro-variations, rendering each loop a flawed echo of the previous one. The most striking moments of the performance, however, occur when the digital feedback loops and the larger acoustic loop of transcription, activation, and recording enter into unexpected phase locks. In these moments, a delicate, self-sustaining pattern emerges from the chaos, repeating itself for a few seconds like a lucid dream before inevitably dissolving back into the acyclical, turbulent sonic flow.

Stuttering Calls of the Unencoded re-imagines the Klavierautomat's fundamental purpose, pushing the instrument to an extreme of resynthetic complexity. This process enacts an alternative McLuhanian principle of reversal, whereby at its limit, the Klavierautomat ceases to be a medium for computational perfection and becomes instead a medium for channelling the very forces that such logic seeks to exorcise. The instrument gives a physical, acoustic voice to the glitches, miscalculations, and spectral residues that emerge from this overloaded digital process, becoming a truly hauntological machine. As the computational system's spectral other, the Klavierautomat renders its internal ghosts audible and tangible, staging the very act of translation as an uncanny and provocative play.

Conclusions

The Klavierautomat reveals a dual aesthetic regime. On one side, a technological sublime of algorithmic precision, velocity, and inhuman consistency emerges. On the other, a hauntological sublime surfaces, in which traces of instability, spectral presence, and flawed translation manifest within the machine's operation. In Heideggerian terms, this duality stages a progressive unconcealment, the essential features of which are summarised in [Table 1](#). This liminal capacity distinguishes the Klavierautomat from other technical objects. Unlike standard musical instruments such as the traditional piano, which conceal their mechanisms within polished cases, and unlike robotic systems designed for

Table 1. The dual aesthetic regime of the Klavierautomat. These poles represent complementary dimensions of a single instrument's expressive range rather than a fixed opposition; in practice, any given work may inhabit both simultaneously or move between them.

	Technological sublime	Hauntological sublime
What is unconcealed The machine operates as	The truth of algorithmic logic A tool for realising flawless logic	The spectral traces of human labour A medium for channelling imperfection
Relation to the human performer	Transcendence: bodily limits rendered obsolete	Haunting: the absent body persists as spectral benchmark
Role of error	Exorcised in pursuit of computational perfection	Summoned as primary aesthetic material
McLuhanian dynamic	Enhancement: the medium fulfils its designed potential	Reversal: the medium becomes a vehicle for the forces its logic seeks to eliminate

seamless mediation, the Klavierautomat deliberately exposes its inner workings. Yet it also diverges from humanoid robots, which actively court the uncanny through deliberate simulation of human presence. The Klavierautomat's uncanniness is subtler, emerging from its very condition as a threshold object. Its exposed solenoids do not pretend to be fingers, yet they depress keys with expressive intention. Its ambiguity is that of a genuine liminal apparatus, suspended between tool and instrument, equipment and work of art, presence and absence, and therein lies its singular aesthetic power.

The theatrical positioning of the Klavierautomat generates a productive frame collision for its audience. Viewers simultaneously encounter the familiar frame of the piano recital and the alien frame of technical demonstration, preventing passive reception and forcing reflection on the nature of performance itself. At the same time, it deliberately appropriates and haunts one of the most historically loaded musical objects, the piano. Through its portability, its parasitic design, and its capacity to possess virtually any acoustic piano, it overlays machinic agency onto a deeply human cultural symbol and turns the familiar into something estranged. This possession stages absence as a performative event, where mechanical agency visibly inhabits the space once reserved for the pianist, giving concrete form to what Goebbels theorised as an 'aesthetics of absence' and making the confrontation with non-human forces the primary dramaturgical focus.

This confrontation carries an ethical charge. Against the grain of capitalist technoscience, which accelerates automation toward the frictionless erasure of everything that resists optimisation, the Klavierautomat's aesthetics of absence operates as a force of negativity rather than affirmation. It refuses to conceal its mechanisms or simulate human presence, and in doing so resists the logic in which robotisation is naturalised as seamless and ideologically neutral. Instead, it stages the latent affectivities of artificiality, eeriness, and estrangement as truthful conditions of its own operation. These affects are themselves revelatory. As Fisher argues, the perspective of the eerie 'can give us access to the forces which govern mundane reality but which are ordinarily obscured' (Fisher 2016, 13), and it is through this eerie disclosure that the Klavierautomat renders perceptible the displacements and spectral residues that optimised systems work to suppress. It is on this alienating ground that post-human subjectivities and collectivities capable of negotiating their relations with machines may begin to take form. As the Xenofeminist Manifesto contends, alienation is not a condition to be remedied but 'an impetus to generate new worlds' (Cuboniks 2018, 0 × 01).

Simondon's philosophy of technology offers a precise account of how such negotiation operates. The instrument carries forward a transductive relation where each performance actualises new configurations from a reservoir of potential shared between humans and technical objects. The composer or live coder does not command the machine from a position of mastery but enters into a coupled becoming, navigating its resistances and emergent tendencies. Agency is distributed across this assemblage of code, mechanism, and acoustic matter, troubling any clear attribution of authorship.

Future directions for the Klavierautomat open along multiple axes. One promising avenue involves staging the instrument alongside live human instrumentalists, making the tension between absence and presence an explicit dramaturgical element. Staging the breathing body of a live musician against the mechanical agency of the Klavierautomat could intensify the frame collision already inherent in its solo performances, creating dialogues between human spontaneity and algorithmic precision. Another trajectory

involves the integration of artificial intelligence to control the instrument. Machine learning systems trained on musical corpora could generate performances that channel statistical ghosts of entire repertoires, collapsing the spectral traces of countless composers and performers into a single mechanical voice.

Pushing into more speculative territory, such developments may unconceal a future-oriented dimension. If computational precision reveals present algorithmic logic and glitches unconceal past human labour, what lies beyond is the machine's capacity to prefigure aesthetic possibilities without human precedent. The Klavierautomat would then enact a reverse haunting, with its present performances already leaving spectral traces conditioning what music and creativity might come to mean. Whether such a future arrives or not, the Klavierautomat already occupies this threshold, an instrument poised between what music has been and what it might become, giving acoustic form to the unresolved entanglement of human and machine.

Notes

1. <http://www.icst.net>
2. <https://ablinger.mur.at/docu11.html>
3. For more information about Arabic music automata, see Zielinski and Weibel 2015.
4. 'Die Vorzüge des Apparats liegen lediglich in seiner absoluten Eindeutigkeit, Klarheit, Sauberkeit und der hochgradigen Präzision – Eigenschaften, die das menschliche Spiel nicht besitzt und auch nicht braucht.' (English translation by the authors.)
5. Live coding is a performative practice in which musicians write and modify computer code in real time to generate or manipulate sound, typically projecting the code on screen for the audience. For a comprehensive account of the practice, see Blackwell et al. 2022.
6. Video: <https://vimeo.com/showcase/11801033>.
7. Video: <https://youtu.be/HrmGOVXBHvE?feature=shared&t=2409>.
8. Key terms used here draw from Simondonian philosophy. Transduction refers to a process of propagation where an activity or structure is passed from one element to the next, amplifying and transforming it along the way. Individuation is the process of becoming through which an entity emerges. A metastable state describes a system in a condition of apparent equilibrium that is nevertheless charged with potential for transformation, where a small input can trigger a phase shift into a new state of organization.
9. SCTweets are a form of creative coding where the entire logic for a piece of music or sound is constrained to the character limit of a tweet (originally 140 characters), encouraging conciseness and ingenuity. Batuhan Bozkurt's work can be found at: <https://earslap.com/>

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